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**A Generalization of an
Inequality of Tchebychev**

In Florentin Smarandache: “Collected Papers”, vol. I (second edition). Ann Arbor (USA): InfoLearnQuest, 2007.

Statement: If $a_i^{(k)} \geq a_{i+1}^{(k)}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$, then:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{k=1}^m a_i^{(k)} \geq \frac{1}{n^m} \prod_{k=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(k)}.$$

Demonstration by recurrence on m .

Case $m = 1$ is obvious: $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(1)} \geq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(1)}$.

In the case $m = 2$, this is the inequality of Tchebychev itself:

If $a_1^{(1)} \geq a_2^{(1)} \geq \dots \geq a_n^{(1)}$ and $a_1^{(2)} \geq a_2^{(2)} \geq \dots \geq a_n^{(2)}$, then:

$$\frac{a_1^{(1)} a_1^{(2)} + a_2^{(1)} a_2^{(2)} + \dots + a_n^{(1)} a_n^{(2)}}{n} \geq \frac{a_1^{(1)} + a_2^{(1)} + \dots + a_n^{(1)}}{n} \times \frac{a_1^{(2)} + \dots + a_n^{(2)}}{n}$$

One supposes that the inequality is true for all the values smaller or equal to m . It is necessary to prove for the rang $m + 1$:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{k=1}^{m+1} a_i^{(k)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\prod_{k=1}^m a_i^{(k)} \right) \cdot a_i^{(m+1)}.$$

This is $\geq \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{k=1}^m a_i^{(k)} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(m+1)} \right) \geq \left(\frac{1}{n^m} \prod_{k=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(k)} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(m+1)} \right)$

and this is exactly $\frac{1}{n^{m+1}} \prod_{k=1}^{m+1} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^{(k)}$ (Quod Erat Demonstrandum).